

Tylophora Alkaloids*

T. R. GOVINDACHARI

CIBA Research Centre, Goregaon, Bombay

THE family *Asclepiadaceae* is a large one comprising over 320 genera and 1700 species.

While many plants belonging to this family have been investigated, alkaloids have been encountered only in a few. Nicotine was isolated¹ from *Asclepias syriaca*. Cryptolepine was isolated from *Cryptolepis triangularis*² and *Cryptolepis sanguinolenta*³. The alkaloids isolated from plants belonging to the genus *Tylophora* form the subject matter of this lecture. Two of these alkaloids, tylophorine and tylocrebrine, have also been isolated from *Ficus septica*, a plant belonging to the Moraceae⁴. The alkaloids of *Cynanchum vincetoxicum* (*Asclepiadaceae*) have been shown to have the same phenanthroindolizidine skeleton as present in the *Tylophora* alkaloids⁵⁻⁸. It is of interest that the closely similar phenanthroquinolizidine system is present in cryptoleurine⁹ isolated from a plant belonging to the Lauraceae, a family far removed botanically from *Asclepiadaceae*.

The Alkaloids of *Tylophora asthmatica*

A. Isolation

Tylophora asthmatica Wight et Arn. (syn. *Tylophora indica*) is a perennial branching climber, belonging to the family *Asclepiadaceae* and growing wild in the plains forests in eastern and southern India. Hooper¹⁰ showed the presence of a crystalline alkaloid but the amount isolated was inadequate for a proper characterization. Ratnagiriswaran and Venkatachalam¹¹ isolated from the plant two alkaloids, tylophorine and tylophorinine, for which they assigned the molecular formula $C_{24}H_{27}O_4N$ and $C_{23}H_{27}O_4N$, respectively. Chopra *et al.*¹² could obtain only tylophorine from *T. asthmatica*, but not tylophorinine, although they obtained a second amorphous base (m.p. 125°-130°C) which was not further characterized. Govindachari *et al.*¹³ were able to isolate both tylophorine and tylophorinine from *T. asthmatica* and the alkaloids were separated by chromatography on alumina. After crystallization from chloroform, tylophorine melted at 286°-287°C (dec.) and had $[\alpha]_D -11.6^\circ$ (c 1.07, $CHCl_3$).

Tylophorinine was purified¹⁴ by rechromatography over alumina and converted to a hydrochloride. The base regenerated from the pure hydrochloride melted at 248°-249°C and had $[\alpha]_D -14.2^\circ$ (c. 1.76, $CHCl_3$). Careful analysis of the base and its salts resulted in the revision of the molecular formula of tylophorinine to $C_{23}H_{25}O_4N$.

Mulchandani *et al.*¹⁵ reported the isolation of a phenolic alkaloid, tylophorinidine from *T. asthmatica*. The base $C_{22}H_{23}O_4N$, M⁺ 365, had m.p. 213°-214°C (dec.), $[\alpha]_D^{25} +108^\circ$ (c 1.91, MeOH). Rao¹⁶ reported the isolation of three minor alkaloids, designated A, B and C, from the plant with the following physical constants:

- Alkaloid A, $C_{22}H_{23}O_5N$, M⁺ 381, m.p. 250°-252°C (dec.),
Alkaloid B, $C_{23}H_{25}O_4N$, M⁺ 379, m.p. 235°-237°C (dec.),
Alkaloid C, $C_{22}H_{23}O_4N$, M⁺ 365, m.p. 253°-255°C (dec.)

During a recent investigation¹⁷, we have isolated three minor constituents, one of them being tylophorinidine. The other two bases were identified as (+)-septicine, $C_{24}H_{29}O_4N$, M⁺ 395, m.p. 136°C, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +38.8^\circ$ (c 1, MeOH) and (+)-isotylocrebrine, $C_{24}H_{27}O_4N$, M⁺ 393, m.p. 212°-214°C, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +22.43^\circ$ (c 1, $CHCl_3$).

B. Tylophorine

1. *Determination of Structure*^{18,19}: Tylophorine, $C_{24}H_{27}O_4N$ (IV), is a tertiary base having four methoxyl groups but no N-methyl group and no easily reducible unsaturation. Its UV-spectrum has maxima at 255, 290, 340 and 352 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.74, 4.49, 3.30, 2.93) indicating the presence of a phenanthrene chromophore.

On submitting tylophorine to the Hofmann degradation, tylophorine-methine, $C_{25}H_{29}O_4N$ (m.p. 190°C) is obtained, which on a second Hofmann degradation yields de-N-methyltylophorinemethine, $C_{26}H_{31}O_4N$ (m.p. 167°C), and a nitrogen-free product, $C_{24}H_{24}O_5$, formed by the replacement of a dimethylamino group in the former by a hydroxyl group. Since the second-stage Hofmann product is still basic it follows that the nitrogen atom in tylophorine is common to two rings.

Tylophorine methiodide is converted by boiling with alkali into the racemic isomethiodide. Tylophorinemethine does not undergo reduction under catalytic hydrogenation conditions, but is transformed to the isomethoxyhydroxide, identified by conversion to the isomethiodide. Reversion of a methine to one of the racemic forms of the quaternary salt from which it is derived has been observed in the case of quinolizidine alkaloids of the canadine type²⁰—a transannular reaction characteristic of eight-, nine-, or ten-membered rings incorporating a nitrogen atom.

* Presidential address to the Indian Chemical Society, 1972.

Treatment of tylophorine with cyanogen bromide yields a crystalline bromocyanamide, which on treatment with sodium borohydride yields a hydroxycyanamide. The latter on hydrolysis with sulfuric acid yields tylophorine, indicating the presence of a 1:4 or 1:5 amino-alcohol system in the compound.

On submitting tylophorine methochloride or isomethochloride to the Emde degradation, isodihydrohomotylophorine, $C_{25}H_{31}O_4N$, is obtained. This can be dehydrogenated with Pd/C to tetrahydroisodihydrohomotylophorine, a nonbasic compound showing a positive Ehrlich test indicating the presence of a pyrrole ring. On catalytic reduction the original isodihydrohomotylophorine is obtained, proving that no change in ring size has occurred during the dehydrogenation. The presence of a five-membered, nitrogen-containing ring is thus established.

Oxidation of the Hofmann degradation product from isodihydrohomotylophorine yields a mixture of acidic products. These can be converted to the corresponding methyl esters and then separated by chromatography into a mono ester, $C_{21}H_{22}O_6$ (m.p. 185° – $186^{\circ}C$), and a diester, $C_{22}H_{22}O_8$ (m.p. 246° – $247^{\circ}C$). The monoester on hydrolysis and decarboxylation yields, 2,3,6,7-tetramethoxy-9-methylphenanthrene (I), identical with an authentic synthetic specimen. The diester is hydrolyzed to a dicarboxylic acid which is also obtained by the oxidation of tylophorine isomethohydroxide with permanganate along with a small amount of an imide, $C_{20}H_{17}O_6N$. The latter was shown to be 2,3,6,7-tetramethoxyphenanthrene-9,10-dicarboxylimide (II) by comparison with a specimen obtained by oxidation of the dihydroisoquinoline (III) synthesized for the purpose from 2,3,6,7-tetramethoxyphenanthrene-9-aldehyde by standard procedures¹⁹.

Vigorous oxidation of tylophorine methiodide with permanganate yields *m*-hemipinic acid as the only isolable product. Oxidation of tylophorinemethine with permanganate in pyridine yields a neutral nitrogenous substance, $C_{25}H_{27}O_5N$ (m.p. 241° – $244^{\circ}C$), formed by the oxidation of a methylene group adjacent to the nitrogen atom to a carbonyl group¹⁸.

On the basis of these degradation studies tylophorine is formulated as 9,11,12,13,13a,14-hexahydro-2,3,6,7-tetramethoxydibenzo[*f*, *h*]pyrrolo-[1,2-*b*] isoquinoline (IV)*. The structures of tylophorinemethine, de-*N*-methyltylophorinemethine, isodihydrohomotylophorine, and tetrahydroisodihydrohomotylophorine can then be depicted as V, VI, VII and VIII respectively.

The Emde degradation of tylophorine methiodide yields a product identical with that obtained from tylophorineisomethiodide. When tylophorinemethine is submitted to the Emde degradation, a compound, $C_{26}H_{33}O_4N$ (m.p. 155° – $156^{\circ}C$), is obtained which may be formulated as IX.

A different product (m.p. $148^{\circ}C$), is obtained by submitting isodihydrohomotylophorine (VII) to the Hofman degradation. Both the compounds yield the same isotetrahydrohomotylophorinemethine on reduction. Since the compound (m.p. $148^{\circ}C$), has a strong band at 10.13μ characteristic of a *trans*-disubstituted ethylenic linkage, it is formulated as the *trans*-isomer corresponding to IX. The double bond in

* The numbering of the parent ring system is shown opposite.

tylophorinmethine forms part of a nine-membered ring and is likely to have the less strained *cis*-configuration²¹. In isodihydrohomotylophorine, on the other hand, no such restriction is present and it gives rise to the more stable *trans* isomer.

Application of the Hofmann degradation to de-N-methyltylophorinmethine (VI) yields a compound, C₂₄H₂₄O₄ (m.p. 181°–188°C), which may be formulated as X or a derived transformation product. This could be formed by attack of base at the doubly allylic position of VI.

2. *Synthesis*^{22,23}: (a) Treatment of 2,3,6,7-tetramethoxy-9-chloromethylphenanthrene with pyrrolidine magnesium bromide yielded 2-(2,3,6,7-tetramethoxy-9-phenanthrylmethyl) pyrrole (XI) which was reduced to the corresponding pyrrolidine. The N-formyl derivative of the latter underwent smooth cyclization with phosphorous oxychloride to the quaternary salt (XII) reduced in good yield to (±)-tylophorine by sodium borohydride. The synthetic compound was resolved through (+)-camphorsulfonic acid into (–)-tylophorine (m.p. 292°C; [α]_D –11.5°), and (+)-tylophorine (m.p. 292°C; [α]_D +12.15°).

The (–)-tylophorine was identical with natural tylophorine²².

XI

XII

(b) A second synthesis of (±)-tylophorine involved the cyclization of the acid (XIII) with PPA and Clemmensen reduction of the derived ketone (XIV)²³.

XIII

XIV

C. Tylophorinine

1. *Determination of Structure*¹⁴: Tylophorinine, C₂₃H₂₅O₄N (XVIIb) is a tertiary base with three methoxyl groups but no N-methyl group. Its UV spectrum with maxima at 258, 287 and 340 mμ (log ε 4.61, 4.34, 2.91) is very similar to that of cryptopleurine, a 2,3,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene derivative⁹. The fourth oxygen atom is present as an alcoholic hydroxyl group, the IR spectrum showing

a band (in liquid petrolatum) at 3.1μ. It forms an acetate with IR bands (CHCl₃) at 5.8 and 8.0μ. Since the UV spectrum of the alkaloid is not changed by addition of alkali, the hydroxyl group is not phenolic.

XV

XVI

XVII

XVIII

a : R = H

b : R = OH

Application of the Hofmann and Emde reactions to tylophorinine did not lead to any useful result. Vigorous oxidation of tylophorinine gave *m*-hemipinic acid as the only isolable product. Mild oxidation of the methiodide yielded an imide, C₁₉H₁₅O₅N (m.p. 297°C), and an acid readily converted to an anhydride and yielding with diazomethane a crystalline diester, C₂₁H₂₀O₇ (m.p. 160°–162°C). The identity of the imide as 2,3,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene-9,10-dicarboxylimide (XV) was established by comparison with a synthetic specimen obtained by oxidation of the dihydroisoquinoline (XVI) synthesized by the standard route from 2,3,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene-9-aldehyde. Further, the diester was shown to be identical with dimethyl 2,3,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene-9,10-dicarboxylate obtained by oxidation of cryptopleurine followed by esterification.

Catalytic hydrogenation of tylophorinine in acetic acid-perchloric acid in the presence of Pd/C yields deoxytylophorinine, C₂₃H₂₅O₃N (m.p. 252°–254°C), by hydrogenolysis of the hydroxyl group. On the assumption that tylophorinine has the same structural framework as tylophorine, this compound can be formulated either as XVIIa or XVIII^{14,24}.

Both the compounds were synthesized^{14,24} by the same route as employed for tylophorine, and deoxytylophorinine was found to correspond to 9,11,12,13,13a,14-hexahydro-3,6,7-trimethoxydibenzo[*f,h*]pyrrolo[1,2-*b*]isoquinoline (XVIIa).

Since tylophorinine does not behave like a carbinoamine and since it suffers hydrogenolysis in acetic acid-perchloric acid, the hydroxyl group is benzylic and can be located uniquely, as shown in XVIIb.

Tylophorinine can therefore be formulated as 9,11,12,13,13a,14-hexahydro-14-hydroxy-3,6,7-trimethoxydi-benzo-[f,h]pyrrolo[1,2-b]isoquinoline (XVIIb).

2. *Synthesis*²⁵: Condensation of 9-chloromethyl-3,6,7-trimethoxyphenanthrene with methyl L-prolinate yielded methyl 3,6,7-trimethoxy-N-(9-phenanthryl-methyl) pyrrolidine-2-carboxylate (XIX). The corresponding acid obtained by hydrolysis was cyclized by polyphosphoric acid to 9,11,12,13,13a,14-hexahydro-3,6,7-trimethoxy-14-oxodibenzo[f,h]pyrrolo[1,2-b]isoquinoline (XX).

Reduction with sodium borohydride yielded a mixture from which one compound (m.p. 246°C), was isolated in a state of purity. Its IR spectrum (KBr, CHCl₃) was identical with that of natural (-)-tylophorinine.

D. Tylophorinidine^{15,17}

Tylophorinidine, C₂₂H₂₃O₄N, was shown by its UV spectrum to have the phenanthroindolizidine skeleton. Its mass spectrum shows a strong peak at m/e 296 (M-69) by a cleavage characteristic of these alkaloids²⁶.

Methylation with diazomethane gave what appeared to be a dimethyl ether. Based on an unconvincing interpretation of the NMR spectrum of diacetyltylophorinidine, the authors preferred structure XXIa for tylophorinidine, the dimethyl ether being XXIb and the diacetate XXIc.

- a : R = H
b : R = Me
c : R = Ae

Structure XXIa leaves unexplained the absorption at 1724 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum of the diacetate. In the NMR spectrum of the diacetate, the lowest

field signals at δ 8.33 and 8.0 have been assigned to the protons at C-1 and C-6 which would be expected to absorb at higher fields than that at C-4.

We have reinvestigated the structure of tylophorinidine. The identity of our alkaloid, isolated by counter-current distribution, was checked by direct comparison with a sample supplied by Dr. Mulchandani.

The UV spectrum of tylophorinidine shows maxima at 260, 287, 313 and 340 mμ (log ε 4.64, 4.41, 3.90, 3.17) and is strikingly similar to that of tylophorinine indicating a 2,3,6-tioxygenated phenanthrene skeleton. The presence of a phenolic hydroxyl group is indicated by the green colouration with ferric chloride and the shift in its UV maxima on addition of alkali. The NMR spectrum of tylophorinidine (in DMSO-d₆) shows the presence of two methoxyl groups at δ 3.80 and 3.95, five aromatic protons at δ 6.55-8.00 and a CH-OH function at δ 4.65.

Its mass spectrum shows M⁺ at m/e 365. The base peak at m/e 296 arises by cleavage of the pyrrolidine ring. A strong peak at m/e 268 arises from m/e 296 by loss of CO and is indicative²³ of the presence of a hydroxyl at C₁₄²³.

Methylation of tylophorinidine with diazomethane gives a monomethyl ether, C₂₃H₂₅O₄N, M⁺ 379, m.p. 229°-231°C (dec.), [α]_D²⁵ +161° (c 1.5, CHCl₃) and not a dimethyl ether as claimed by Mulchandani *et al.*¹⁵ Its NMR spectrum (in CDCl₃) shows the presence of three methoxyl groups, a CH-OH function and a hydroxyl (exchanged with D₂O) and five aromatic protons assigned as shown in Table 1.

The methyl ether still has an alcoholic hydroxyl group, acetylation leading to a monoacetate, m.p. 176°-177°C, M⁺ 421, [α]_D²⁵ +158° (c 1.5, CHCl₃). Its NMR spectrum was virtually identical with that of acetyltylophorinine.

Acetylation of tylophorinidine gives a diacetate, m.p. 193°-195°C (dec.). Its IR spectrum, ν_{max}^{KBr} 1760, 1730 cm⁻¹, clearly showed the presence of a phenolic acetate and an alcoholic acetate group. Its NMR spectrum shows two acetate groups at δ 2.39 and 2.12, the former being due to the phenolic acetate group.

Catalytic hydrogenolysis of tylophorinidine gives a desoxy base, C₂₂H₂₃O₃N, M⁺ 349, m.p. 214°-218°C. *O*-Methyltylophorinidine on hydrogenolysis gives (±)-desoxytylophorinine (XVIIa) hence showing that it is a diastereoisomer of tylophorinine. Of the three possible positions 3,6 and 7 for the location of the phenolic hydroxyl in tylophorinidine, position 6 is favoured on the basis of the NMR spectra of diacetyltylophorinidine and acetyl *O*-methyltylophorinidine (Table 1). The protons at C-1, C-2, C-4 and C-8 are found at approximately the same chemical shifts in both the compounds. The proton at C-5, however, which occurs at δ 7.88 in acetyl *O*-methyltylophorinidine, is shifted to δ 8.18 in the diacetate. Since in comparison to a methoxy group, the acetoxy group has a deshielding influence of approximately 0.22 ppm on the *ortho*-proton²⁷, position 6 is favoured

TABLE 1. NMR SPECTRAL DATA

Proton	<i>O</i> -Methyltylophorinidine (CDCl ₃)	<i>O</i> -Methyltylophorinidine (DMSO-d ₆)	Tylophorinine (DMSO-d ₆)	Acetyl <i>O</i> -methyltylophorinidine (CDCl ₃)	Diacetyltylophorinidine (CDCl ₃)
C-1	8.33 (d) (<i>J</i> = 9)	8.20 (d) (<i>J</i> = 9)	8.15 (d) (<i>J</i> = 9)	7.84 (d) (<i>J</i> = 9)	7.80 (d) (<i>J</i> = 9)
C-2	7.16 (dd) (<i>J</i> = 9,2)	7.18 (dd) (<i>J</i> = 9,2)	7.12 (dd) (<i>J</i> = 9,2)	7.20 (dd) (<i>J</i> = 9,2)	7.18 (dd) (<i>J</i> = 9,2)
C-4	7.55 (d) (<i>J</i> = 2)	7.85 (d) (<i>J</i> = 2)	7.86 (d) (<i>J</i> = 2)	7.85 (d) (<i>J</i> = 2)	7.77 (d) (<i>J</i> = 2)
C-5	7.33 (s)	7.81 (s)	7.88 (s)	7.88 (s)	8.18 (s)
C-8	5.70 (s)	6.40 (s)	6.77 (s)	7.16 (s)	7.20 (s)
C-14	4.60 (br)	4.68 (br)	4.70 (br)	6.66 (d) (<i>J</i> = 2)	6.62 (d) (<i>J</i> = 2)
OMe	4.02, 3.98, 3.63	4.0 (6H), 3.75 (3H)	3.98 (6H), 3.83	4.09, 4.04, 3.97	3.97 (6H)
OH	5.90	—	—	—	—
OAc	—	—	—	2.13	2.39, 2.12

for the acetoxy group. This leads to structure XXIIa for tylophorinidine, XXIIb for the methyl ether, XXIIc for acetyl-*O*-methyltylophorinidine and XXII d for the diacetate.

XXII

- a : R₁ = R₂ = H
 b : R₁ = Me; R₂ = H
 c : R₁ = Me; R₂ = Ac
 d : R₁ = R₂ = Ac

The NMR spectrum of *O*-methyltylophorinidine is strikingly different from that of its diastereoisomer tylophorinine (Table 1). In the former, a change of solvent from CDCl₃ to DMSO-d₆ results in an upfield shift of 0.13 ppm for C-1 and downfield shifts of 0.3, 0.48 and 0.7 ppm for C-4, C-5 and C-8 respectively. In CDCl₃, the C-8 proton appears at an abnormally high field at δ 5.7 as a singlet. In the acetate (in CDCl₃), the C-8 proton is shifted downfield by 1.46 ppm.

Neither the C₁₄-OH nor the lone pair of electrons in nitrogen can influence the chemical shift of C-8 proton. The phenomenon may be explained if *O*-methyltylophorinidine exists as a dimer with two molecules being held together by hydrogen bonding between the hydroxyl of one and the nitrogen of the other. This would be facilitated by an axial disposition of the hydroxyl group. In the NMR spectra of both acetyl *O*-methyltylophorinidine and acetyltylophorinine, the C-14 proton is coupled with the C-13a proton to the extent of 2-3 Hz ruling out a *trans*-diaxial relationship in either compound.

The stereostructure (XXIII) is favoured for *O*-methyltylophorinidine, tylophorinine being assigned the diastereoisomeric structure XXIV.

XXIII

XXIV

Dreiding models indicate that it is easy to build up the hydrogen-bonded dimer of XXIII and that in this dimer, the protons at C-4, C-5 and C-8 are mutually shielded by the two molecules, as also the methoxyl at C-7, whereas the proton at C-1 may be slightly deshielded. A polar solvent like DMSO reduces the propensity for hydrogen bonding and leads to more 'normal' chemical shifts. Hydrogen-bonding is totally abolished upon acetylation or by hydrogenolysis and acetyl *O*-methyltylophorinidine and desoxytylophorinine show 'normal' chemical shifts.

E. Minor alkaloids isolated by Rao *et al.*¹⁶

Of the three minor alkaloids recently reported by Rao *et al.*¹⁶, alkaloid B, C₂₃H₂₅O₄N, m.p. 235°-237°C (dec.), was found to be nortylophorine since it gave tylophorine on methylation. Alkaloid C, m.p. 253°-

XXV

XXVI

255°C (d), C₂₂H₂₃O₄N, is isomeric with tylophorinidine and gives tylophorinine on methylation. The

phenolic hydroxyl in alkaloid C was assigned to either position 3 or 6. Optical rotations of alkaloid C and derivatives are not reported but it is likely that this is identical with tylophorinidine, the higher m.p. being due to solvation. Alkaloid C has also been isolated from *Tylophora dalzellii*¹⁶.

F. Minor alkaloids isolated by Govindachari *et al.*¹⁷

1. *Determination of structure*: Of the two other minor alkaloids isolated by us, the one melting at 136°C appears to be a purer form of the amorphous base, m.p. 125°–130°C, reported by Chopra *et al.*¹² The alkaloid, C₂₄H₂₉O₄N, M⁺ 395, is identical in UV, IR and NMR spectra with septicine (XXV) which was first isolated from *Ficus septica* (4) and synthesized by two methods^{28,29}. Its rotation, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +38.8^\circ$, shows that it is antipodal to the base obtained from *Ficus septica*.

The other minor alkaloid, m.p. 212°–214°C, C₂₄H₂₇O₄N, has been found to be identical with isotylocrebrine (XXVI) which had been synthesized in connection with the structure elucidation of tylocrebrine (see under *T. crebriflora*)³⁰.

2. *Synthesis of septicine*: Septicine has been synthesized by two methods:

(a) The diester (XXVII) obtained from the chloride (XXVII) and ethyl 2-pyrrolidinyl acetate was subjected to Dieckmann cyclisation to give the ketone (XXIX). This was reacted with veratryl lithium to give the carbinol (XXX). Dehydration with KHSO₄ gave (±)-septicine²⁸.

(b) Reaction of the chloro compound (XXXI) with L-prolinol gave the amino alcohol (XXXII)

The mesylate of the latter on treatment with sodium hydride in DMF gave (–)-septicine²⁹.

The Alkaloids of *Tylophora crebriflora*

A. Isolation^{30,31}.

Tylophora crebriflora S.T. Blake (*T. floribunda* Benth.) occurs in North Queensland. Extraction of the plant material with hot methanol afforded the crude mixture of alkaloids which was purified by chromatography on cellulose powder using propanol-2*N*-acetic acid as the eluent. Further purification by repeated chromatography yielded tylophorine (R_f 0.5 in butan-1-ol-acetic acid 97 : 3) and tylocrebrine (R_f 0.2 in the same solvent system) (m.p. 218°–220°C; $[\alpha]_D^{21} -45^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ (c 0.1, CHCl₃). (+)-Tylocrebrine isolated from *Ficus septica* Frost. f. was found⁴ to have m.p. 220°–222°C and $[\alpha]_D^{22} +20.5^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ (c 0.8, CHCl₃).

Rao *et al.*³¹ isolated six additional alkaloids from *T. crebriflora* by using counter-current distribution—Alkaloid A, C₂₄H₂₇O₅N, m.p. 212°–214°C, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -32^\circ$ (c 1, CHCl₃), λ_{max} 262, 285 sh, 305 sh mμ (log ε 4.84, 4.43, 4.03); Alkaloid B, C₂₃H₂₅O₄N, m.p. 222°–224°C, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -63^\circ$ (c 1, CHCl₃), λ_{max} 262, 284 sh, 302 sh mμ (log ε 4.82, 4.39, 4.06); Alkaloid C, C₂₃H₂₅O₅N, m.p. 223°–225°C, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +34^\circ$ (c 1, CHCl₃), λ_{max} 262, 265 sh, 303 sh mμ (log ε 4.78, 4.36, 4.14); Alkaloid D, C₂₅H₂₉O₆N, m.p. 186°–188°C, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -16.5^\circ$ (c 1, CHCl₃), λ_{max} 262, 282 sh mμ (log ε 4.84, 4.41); Alkaloid E, C₂₅H₂₉O₅N, m.p. 198°–200°C, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -69^\circ$ (c 1, CHCl₃), λ_{max} 263 mμ (log ε 4.88); Alkaloid F, C₂₄H₂₉O₄N, m.p. 137°–138°C, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -42.5^\circ$ (c 1, CHCl₃), λ_{max} 240 sh, 288 mμ (log ε 4.20, 4.00).

B. Tylocrebrine.

1. *Determination of structure*³⁰: Tylocrebrine, C₂₄H₂₇O₄N, (m.p. 218°–220°C), is a tertiary base having four methoxyl groups, no N-methyl group and no easily reducible unsaturation. Its UV spectrum with absorption maxima at 263, 342, and 360 mμ (log ε 4.81, 3.25, 3.09) is practically superposable on that of 3,4,6,7-tetramethoxy-9-methylphenanthrene. The IR spectrum confirms the absence of OH, NH or carbonyl functions. Since the alkaloid is isomeric and occurs jointly with tylophorine, it may be assumed to have the same phenanthroindolizidine system; on the basis of the UV spectrum two structures (XXXIII or XXVI) may be proposed. A choice between the two structures was made by synthesis as described in the next section.

2. *Synthesis*³⁰: The synthesis of 9,11,12,13,13a,14-hexahydro-2,3,5,6-tetramethoxydibenzo [f, h] pyrrolo [1,2-b] isoquinoline (XXXIII), and the 3,4,6,7-tetramethoxy isomer (XXVI) were accomplished by the

same sequence of reactions as employed for tylophorine, starting from methyl-3,4,6,7-tetramethoxyphenanthrene-9-carboxylate and methyl-2,3,5,6-tetramethoxyphenanthrene-9-carboxylate, respectively. Natural tylocrebrine was found to correspond to structure XXXIII.

C. Structure of the minor alkaloids³².

Alkaloid A on hydrogenolysis gives a desoxybase, $C_{24}H_{27}O_4N$, supporting the presence of a hydroxyl at C-14. The desoxybase, from its NMR spectrum, appear to be identical with isotylocrebrine (XXVI). Acetylation of alkaloid A give an acetate, m.p. 197°–198°C. Alkaloid B was found to have three methoxy groups and a phenolic hydroxyl and on methylation gave isotylocrebrine (XXVI). Alkaloid C on methylation gave alkaloid A and these interconversions lead to structures XXXIV, XXXVa and XXXVb and for alkaloids A, B and C respectively.

The assignment of the hydroxyl in alkaloids B and C was based on the positive Gibb's test given by these. Oxidation of alkaloid A with ceric sulphate gave a red product assigned the *ortho*quinone structure XXXVI.

Alkaloids D and E contain five methoxys each, hydrogenolysis of D yielding E. From a consideration of their NMR spectra, structures XXXVIIa and XXXVIIb are favoured for D and E respectively.

Alkaloid F was identified as (–)-septicine (XXV).

The Alkaloids of *Cyananchem vincetoxicum*

Pailer and Streicher²⁶ isolated an 'alkaloid A' from *Vincetoxicum officinale* Moench (syn. *Cyananchem vincetoxicum* L. Pers) and suggested that this was identical with antofine, isolated by Platonova *et al.*³³ from *Antitoxicum funebre* Boiss and Kotschy. Wiegrebbe *et al.*^{5,6} have re-isolated this alkaloid and shown that this is identical with isodesoxytylophorinine (XVIII) which had been synthesized earlier²⁴.

Besides antofine and tylophorine, Wiegrebbe *et al.* have isolated a minor alkaloid (XXXVIII) which on hydrogenolysis gives antofine. A minor phenolic alkaloid obtained from the plant has been shown to have structures (XXXIX) by synthesis⁷.

The absolute configuration R at C-13a in antofine (XVIII) follows from the identification of D-proline among the products of vigorous ozonolysis in acidic solution⁸.

Chauncy and Gellert³⁴ have described new syntheses of (±)-antofine (isodesoxytylophorinine), (±)-tylocrebrine and (±)-tylophorine which are slight variations of the previous syntheses.

Biogenesis^{18, 26, 35, 36, 37}

The phenanthroindolizine alkaloids can be visualized as arising by the condensation of two molecules of dihydroxyphenylalanine or one molecule of dihydroxyphenylalanine and one of tyrosine (or their

equivalents, the corresponding benzoyl acetic and phenyl pyruvic (acids) with ornithine (or its equivalent, γ -aminobutyraldehyde).

The joint occurrence of tylophorine and tylocrebrine with the secophenanthroindolizidine alkaloid septicine in *Ficus septica*⁴ and *Tylophora* Spp. lends support to the biogenetic scheme outlined above. It is also of interest that septicine is transformed to a mixture of tylophorine and tylocrebrine on UV irradiation.

As a result of recent biosynthetic work, the biosynthesis illustrated in Scheme I has been proposed for tylophorine^{36,37}. The evidence came from incorporation experiments in *Tylophora asthmatica* plants with [2-¹⁴C]phenylalanine and [2-¹⁴C]tyrosine respectively. The alkaloid from each feeding was degraded to establish the labelling pattern shown below. Thus, tyrosine and phenylalanine are incorporated by completely separate pathways, probably as a C₆-C₂ unit in each case, to provide ring A+C-10+C-6 and ring B+C-9+C-7 respectively. The scheme employs a Δ^1 -pyrroline unit derived from ornithine; specifically labelled ornithine gave rise to radioactive tylophorine but the pattern of incorporation has not yet been established.

Scheme 1

Biological Activity of *Tylophora* Alkaloids

The pharmacology of tylophorine was studied by Chopra *et al.*¹³ Tylophorine is toxic to *Paramecium caudatum* in a dilution of 1 : 50,000. It is lethal to frogs at a dose of 0.4 mg/kg but toxicity to mice and guinea pigs is very small. It has a paralyzing action on the heart muscles but a stimulating action on the muscles of the blood vessels. The initial drop in blood pressure and subsequent rise to a level above normal on administration of tylophorine is thus explained.

Tylocrebrine shows high activity against lymphoid leukemia L 1210 in mice, the best results being obtained at a dose level of 10 mg/kg.³⁸

Unexpected irreversible central nervous system toxicity shown in the clinic resulted in the drug's withdrawal from tests.

Shivpuri *et al.*³⁹ have found that the leaves of *T. asthmatica* are effective in the treatment of allergic diseases, particularly bronchial asthma.

The powerful vesicant action of these alkaloids has been commented upon by all the investigators^{11,14,30}.

Alkaloid C isolated by Rao *et al.* from *T. asthmatica* showed significant activity in murine leukemia (L-1210 system) at a dose of 6-8 mg/kg.¹⁶

References

1. L. MARION, *Can. J. Res.*, 1939, B17, 21.
2. E. CLINQUART, *Bull. Acad. Roy. Med. Belg.*, 1929, [5] 9, 627; cf. *Chem. Abstr.*, 1940, 24, 1139.
3. E. GELLERT, RAYMOND-HAMET and E. SCHLITTLER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1951, 34, 642.
4. J. H. RUSSEL, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1963, 50, 443.
5. W. WIEGREBE, L. FABER, H. BROCKMANN JR., H. BUDZIKIEWICZ and U. KRÜGER, *Ann.*, 1969, 721, 154.
6. W. WIEGREBE, H. BUDZIKIEWICZ and L. FABER, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1970, 303, 1009.
7. W. WIEGREBE, L. FABER and H. BUDZIKIEWICZ, *Ann.*, 1970, 733, 125.
8. W. WIEGREBE, L. FABER and TH. BREYHAN, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1971, 304, 188.
9. E. GELLERT and N. V. RIGGS, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1954, 7, 113; J. FRIDRICHSONS and A. MATHIESON, *Nature*, 1954, 173, 732.
10. D. HOOPER, *Pharm. J.*, 1891, [1] 21, 617.
11. A. N. RATNAGIRISWARAN and K. VENKATACHALAM, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1935, 22, 433; cf. *Chem. Abstr.*, 1935, 29, 8229.
12. R. N. CHOPRA, N. N. GHOSH, J. B. BOSE and S. GHOSH, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1937, 275, 236.
13. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, B. R. PAI and K. NAGARAJAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2801.
14. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, B. R. PAI, I. S. RAGADE, S. RAJAPPA and N. VISWANATHAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, 14, 288.
15. N. B. MULCHANDANI, S. S. IYER and L. P. BADHEKA, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1971, 505.
16. K. V. RAO, R. A. WILSON and B. CUMMINGS, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1971, 60, 1725.
17. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, N. VISWANATHAN, J. RADHAKRISHNAN, B. R. PAI, S. NATARAJAN, and P. S. SUBRAMANIAM *Unpublished work*.
18. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, M. V. LAKSHMIKANTHAM, K. NAGARAJAN and B. R. PAI, *Tetrahedron*, 1958, 4, 311.
19. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, M. V. LAKSHMIKANTHAM, B. R. PAI and S. RAJAPPA, *Tetrahedron*, 1960, 9, 53.
20. F. L. PYMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 817; A. VOSS and J. GADAMER, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1910, 248, 43.
21. A. T. BLUMQUIST, L. A. LIU and J. C. BOHREN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 3643.
22. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, M. V. LAKSHMIKANTHAM and S. RAJADURAI, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, 14, 284.
23. R. B. HERBERT and C. J. MOODY, *Chem. Comm.*, 1970, 121.
24. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, I. S. RAGADE and N. VISWANATHAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1356.
25. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, B. R. PAI, S. PRABHAKAR and T. S. SAVITRI, *Tetrahedron*, 1965, 21, 2573.
26. M. PAILER and W. STREICHER, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1965, 96, 1094.
27. L. M. JACKMAN, 'Applications of NMR Spectroscopy in Organic Chemistry', p. 202, Pergamon Press, London, 1969.
28. T. R. GOVINDACHARI and N. VISWANATHAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1970, 26, 715.
29. J. H. RUSSEL and H. HUNZIKER, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1969, 4035.
30. E. GELLERT, T. R. GOVINDACHARI, M. V. LAKSHMIKANTHAM, I. S. RAGADE, R. RUDZATS and N. VISWANATHAN *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1008.
31. K. V. RAO, R. WILSON and B. CUMMINGS, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1970, 59, 1501.

T. R. GOVINDACHARI : TYLOPHORA ALKALOIDS

32. K. V. RAO, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1970, **59**, 1608.
33. T. F. PLATONOVA, A. D. KUZOVKOV and P. S. MASSAGETOW, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1958, **28**, 3131; *Chem. Abstrs.*, 1959, **53**, 7506d.
34. B. CHAUNCY and E. GELLEERT, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1970, **23**, 2503.
35. E. WENKERT, *Experientia*, 1959, **15**, 165.
36. N. B. MULCHANDANI, S. S. IYER and L. P. BADHEKA, *Phytochemistry*, 1969, **8**, 1931.
37. N. B. MULCHANDANI, S. S. IYER and L. P. BADHEKA, *Phytochemistry*, 1971, **10**, 1047.
38. E. GELLEERT and R. RUDZATS, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, **7**, 361.
39. D. N. SHIVPURI, M. P. MENON and D. PRAKASH, *J. Ass. Physicians, India*, 1968, **16**, 9; *J. Allergy (U.S.A.)*, 1969, **43**, 145.